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Benefits of local concerted strategic planning and teaching accountability in budget management for users

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Received: 11/10/2023 Accepted: 12/12/2023 Published: 28/12/2023

SummaryThe proposal to implement concerted strategic planning at the local level and accountability in budget management constitutes a comprehensive and promising approach to improve the satisfaction of users of public services. It had a qualitative approach, approaching action research, as they perceived the benefits of local concerted strategic planning and teaching of accountability in budget management for users as a desire of the residents, in this sense the proposal could also promote the confidence of the residents. The implementation of concerted strategic planning at the local level, together with the promotion of learning and accountability in budget management, represents an opportunity to improve the quality of life of local communities. By combining these elements, a more transparent, efficient and oriented public management model can be built to the needs of citizens.

Keywords: Benefits, Strategic planning, local, teaching, accounts, management

Beneficios para los usuarios de la planificación estratégica local concertada y de la responsabilidad docente en la gestión presupuestaria

Resumen: La propuesta de implantar la planificación estratégica local concertada y la rendición de cuentas pedagógica en la gestión presupuestaria es un enfoque global y prometedor para mejorar la satisfacción de los usuarios de los servicios públicos. Tuvo un enfoque cualitativo, acercándose a la investigación-acción, ya que los beneficios de la planificación estratégica local concertada y la enseñanza de la rendición de cuentas en la gestión presupuestaria para los usuarios fueron percibidos como un deseo de la población, en este sentido la propuesta también puede promover la confianza de la población. La aplicación de la planificación estratégica local concertada, junto con la promoción del aprendizaje y la rendición de cuentas en la gestión presupuestaria, representa una oportunidad para mejorar la calidad de vida de las comunidades locales. Combinando estos elementos se puede construir un modelo de gestión pública más transparente, eficiente y orientado al ciudadano.

Palabras clave: Beneficios, Planificación estratégica, Local, Enseñanza, Cuentas, Gestión.

Benefícios do planejamento estratégico local conjunto e da responsabilidade docente na gestão orçamentária para os usuários

Resumo A proposta de implementar o planejamento estratégico local concertado e a responsabilização na gestão orçamentária é uma abordagem abrangente e promissora para melhorar a satisfação dos usuários de serviços públicos. Teve uma abordagem qualitativa, aproximando-se da pesquisa-ação, uma vez que os benefícios do planejamento estratégico local concertado e do ensino da accountability na gestão orçamentária para os usuários foram percebidos como um desejo da população, nesse sentido a proposta também pode promover a confiança da população. A implementação do planejamento estratégico local concertado, juntamente com a promoção do aprendizado e da responsabilidade na gestão orçamentária, representa uma oportunidade para melhorar a qualidade de vida das comunidades locais. Ao combinar esses elementos, é possível construir um modelo de gestão pública mais transparente, eficiente e voltado para o cidadão.

Palavras-chave: Benefícios, Planejamento estratégico, Local, Ensino, Contabilidade, Gestão

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I. Introduction

The proposal to implement concerted strategic planning at the local level, added to the promotion of teaching accountability in budget management, constitutes a comprehensive and promising approach to improve the satisfaction of users of public services. This combination of elements allows local communities to actively participate in defining their priorities, ensuring that residents can perceive that resources are allocated to the areas they need most and generating a greater sense of ownership and commitment on the part of citizens. which generates well-being in users and residents, by also evidencing the willingness of municipal workers to share their knowledge, by wanting to teach accountability for budget management.

1.1. Research related to concerted strategic planning for management According to Ropa-Carrión, Brígido, & Alama-Flores, Marcos. (2022) In the context of concerted strategic planning for management, this article delves into the nature and evolution of the concept of management. The central importance of management in the contemporary world is highlighted, as it is the engine that drives the strategic activities of organizations and contributes to social development. The study presents an exhaustive analysis of the different definitions of management, contrasting the various theoretical and scientific perspectives. Likewise, clear conceptual distinctions are established between management and administration, as well as between planned strategic management and strategic management.

The research categorizes management approaches into three large groups:

- Classic approach: Focused on the efficiency and optimization of production processes.
- Systemic approach: Considers the organization as a complex system interrelated with its environment.
- Complex holistic approach: It adopts a comprehensive vision, encompassing human, social and environmental factors in organizational management.

With respect to concerted strategic planning for results-based management in public procurement. Strategic planning for results-based management in public procurement must consider the following aspects Vaicilla et al., (2020):

Definition of objectives and goals: The objectives and goals of public procurement must be aligned with the general objectives and goals of the entity.

Environment analysis: The environmental analysis must identify internal and external factors that may affect public procurement.

Identification of necessary resources: Planning must identify the human, financial and technological resources necessary to achieve the objectives and goals.

Design of the hiring process: The hiring process must be designed in a way that is efficient, effective and transparent.

Monitoring and evaluation: The hiring process must be monitored and evaluated to ensure that objectives and goals are met. Problems of strategic planning for results-based management in public procurement

Concerted strategic planning for results-based management in Peru: In Peru, some efforts have been made

to improve strategic planning for results-based management in public procurement. For example, the Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF) has developed a tool called "Public Procurement Planner", which helps public entities plan their procurement processes.

1.2. Research related to Teaching accountability

Bermudez Castillo, A. (2023) analyzed the accountability model implemented by the Public Ministry of Costa Rica between 2018 and 2021. Through a documentary analysis, the different stages of the public policy cycle of this model were evaluated, identifying both its advances and its limitations. The results show that the model has managed to establish a standard in terms of the definition and structure of accountability reports, which has allowed opening spaces for citizen participation. However, aspects that require improvement were identified, such as administrative and professional supervisory support, even the evaluation is about this aspect, because to evaluate accountability learning it is necessary to have knowledge about accountability.

Through interviews and focus groups with various actors involved, both the advances and limitations of this model were identified. The research concludes that, despite the efforts made, there is a negative and contradictory perception about the benefits of this model, and there is a lack of solid evidence about its contribution to the improvement of municipal management. Measures are proposed to improve the implementation of a comprehensive management system, based on a collaborative and intergovernmental process, and complemented with quality controls.

II. Methodology

The research was carried out with a qualitative approach, through an action research approach. Some of the co-authors usually work in public activities, and perceived the benefits of local concerted strategic planning and teaching of accountability in budget management for users as a desire of the residents, in this sense the proposal may also foster the confidence of residents or users of the municipality, about the way in which strategic planning is carried out, but it is important the possibility for residents to demonstrate the willingness of municipal workers to share their knowledge about the mentioned areas, which generates in the residents, trust in management and emotional well-being

A documentary and content analysis of various investigations related to local concerted strategic planning and Teaching of accountability in budget management was carried out. Previous models and experiences were examined, which allowed us to understand and interpret the perception of the residents of a community

In addition, research related to this research was analyzed and studies on knowledge management were carried out; Convergences were identified between these perspectives and key aspects for the research proposal. The importance of relationships between actors and the dissemination of knowledge was highlighted. Consequently, a comprehensive literature review was used to build a solid theoretical foundation and contextualize the research within the state of the art.

Auscultation of perception of some residents: Through this method it was possible to verify that public servants do not contemplate in their activities strategic planning of activities that involve the systematic use, for example, of unknown sports tiles. This shows that we must work more on trust and rapprochement with residents to share aspects of public management and management for results; so that they perceive that the results-based budget can be aligned with said management for the benefit of the population.

Open survey on knowledge linked to research: From this method it was determined that the residents are unaware of the strategic planning processes: Determine the strategic position, Prioritize objectives, Develop a strategic plan, Execute, manage the plan; finally Review and modify the plan. The most

knowledgeable residents state that they knew this planning only briefly; In this sense, it made it difficult for them to plan activities, specifically those in the sports sector (as they are the ones that present the greatest attraction to residents), although it is considered that the survey had a formative nature by mentioning the processes for strategic planning, and knowledge of accountability. accounts, which express that they will take it into consideration.

Approach to Methodological Triangulation: After analyzing the results of these methods, the following preliminary conclusions have been reached.

- All methods agree that there was superficial knowledge about management, considering that strategic planning and knowledge of accountability is important to consider sports activities for the benefit of the population.
- In the interview, it is agreed that knowledge of the strategic planning processes and knowledge of accountability is necessary: Determine the strategic position, Prioritize objectives, Develop a strategic plan, Execute, manage the plan; finally Review and modify the plan.

III. Results

According to the dialogues and open interviews, the following results were reached, that to carry out strategic planning and knowledge of accountability, the following must be taken into consideration (indicated below):

3.1. *Local Concerted Strategic Planning:*

- Citizen Participation: Including the community in the planning process ensures that the real needs of citizens are considered and addressed.
- Focus on Results: By establishing clear and measurable objectives, it is easier to monitor progress and evaluate the impact of public policies.
- Alignment with Local Development: Strategic planning must be aligned with local development plans, ensuring a coherent and long-term vision.

3.2. *Learning and Accountability in Budget Management:*

- Transparency: Publishing budget information in a clear and accessible manner fosters citizen confidence in public institutions.
- Continuous Evaluation: Periodic evaluation of results allows us to identify areas for improvement and adjust strategies accordingly.
- Accountability Mechanisms: The implementation of accountability mechanisms, such as public hearings and citizen evaluations, strengthens participatory democracy.

3.3. *Benefits expected by residents*

- Greater User Satisfaction: By allocating resources to community priorities, the quality and efficiency of public services is improved.
- Strengthening Local Governance: Citizen participation and transparency in budget management contribute to more democratic and effective governance.
- Improvement of Public Management: The focus on results and continuous evaluation drive continuous improvement of processes and procedures.
- Greater Efficiency in the Use of Resources: Strategic planning allows you to optimize the use of resources, avoiding duplication and allocating funds to the most priority activities.

3.4. *User Perspectives*

- **Training:**It is essential to train public officials and citizens to participate effectively in planning and evaluation processes.
- **Accessible Information:**Budget information must be presented in a clear and simple manner, using language accessible to all audiences.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:**A robust monitoring and evaluation system is required to measure the progress and impact of the initiatives implemented.
- **Continued Participation:**Citizen participation must be encouraged continuously, beyond the initial planning moments.

IV. Discussion

In comparison to the present investigation, there are the following investigations:

Tumi Quispe, JE (2020). in yourA study carried out in the municipal government of Puno between 2011 and 2018 reveals that the accountability mechanisms are partial and unrepresentative. Despite the existence of public hearings, access to detailed information on public investment and budget execution is limited and presented with reluctance. The main findings indicate that it is important:

- **Political will:**The effectiveness of accountability depends largely on the political will of municipal authorities.
- **Participatory mechanisms:**Citizen participation mechanisms, such as public hearings, are limited and do not guarantee broad representation of the population.
- **Added information:**The information presented in public hearings is generally very general and does not allow a detailed analysis of municipal management.
- **Limited participation:**Participants in public hearings are usually specific actors, such as directors of management committees or supporters of the municipal authority.

It is perceived thatTo improve accountability in municipal governments, it is necessary:

- **Strengthen transparency:**It is necessary to expand access to public information, facilitating the consultation of detailed data on municipal management through digital platforms.
- **Promote citizen participation:**More inclusive participation mechanisms must be implemented that allow all citizens, regardless of their level of knowledge or resources, to participate in accountability processes.
- **Establish clear and measurable indicators:**Accountability must be based on specific and measurable indicators that allow the performance of municipal authorities to be evaluated.
- **Train public officials:**It is essential to train municipal officials in communication and citizen participation techniques so that they can provide clear and concise information to citizens.
- **Audit independently:**Independent audits should be carried out on a regular basis to verify the information presented by municipal authorities.

That is to say,To improve accountability in municipal governments, it is necessary to promote greater transparency, citizen participation, and evidence-based accountability. This will

strengthen democracy and ensure that public resources are used efficiently and effectively for the benefit of the population.

Furthermore, learning accountability is important, as it is a valuable intangible within institutions, as indicated by Lazos and Olivé (2016), mentioning that in the knowledge society it must be intercultural, participatory and sustainable. These principles must guide the development of the knowledge society. Consequently, the implementation of concerted strategic planning is essential for municipalities to achieve their objectives; even more so when results-based management is directly linked to the execution of works as indicated by administrator, administrator, & Garay Paucar, EZ (2023)

Also in contrast to the present research Ropa-Carrión, Brígido, & Alama-Flores, Marcos. (2022) presents a solid foundation for understanding management as a dynamic and multifaceted process. By analyzing the different theoretical and practical perspectives, the importance of management as a key tool for organizational success and sustainable development is evident. The same ones that emphasize the relevance of management in the context of strategic planning, highlighting the diversity of approaches and the importance of understanding key conceptual distinctions.

Also according to Bermudez Castillo, A. (2023) the accountability of management in Governments is linked to Emotional Stability by mentioning that accountability in the Public Ministry of Costa Rica presents relevant implications for small local governments and for the emotional stability of workers and neighbors. .

Implications for small local governments:

- Transparency and trust: Implementing a similar accountability model in small local governments can increase transparency and citizens' trust in their institutions.
- Management improvement: By establishing accountability mechanisms, local governments can improve their resource management and decision making.
- Citizen participation: Accountability models encourage citizen participation, allowing citizens to know and evaluate the performance of their representatives.
- Corruption prevention: Accountability is a key tool to prevent corruption and ensure administrative honesty.

Impact on the emotional stability of workers and neighbors:

- Stress reduction: Transparency and clarity in management can reduce stress and uncertainty in both municipal workers and residents, by allowing them to know the reasons behind decisions and progress in project implementation.
- Improvement of the work environment: A transparent and participatory work environment can improve the work environment and increase employee motivation.
- Strengthening the social fabric: Citizen participation and transparency in management can strengthen the social fabric and generate greater cohesion in communities.

Additional considerations:

- Adaptation to local contexts: Accountability models must be adapted to the specific characteristics and needs of each local government.
- Training: It is essential to train public officials and citizens to ensure the effective implementation of accountability models.

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- **Monitoring and evaluation:**It is necessary to establish monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to guarantee the continuous improvement of accountability processes.

That is to say, The experience of the Public Ministry of Costa Rica demonstrates that accountability is a valuable tool to strengthen democracy, improve public management and increase citizens' confidence in their institutions. Small local governments can benefit significantly from the implementation of accountability models adapted to their realities, thus contributing to improving the quality of life of their inhabitants and strengthening social stability.

Although the intention is to improve municipal management and services, the results obtained so far are not as expected. This raises important questions about the effectiveness of public policies designed to improve local governance and their implications for small local governments and the emotional stability of workers and neighbors:

- **Collaborative approach:**Promote greater collaboration between different levels of government, universities and civil society organizations to design and implement management models more appropriate to local realities.
- **Continuous evaluation:**Implement continuous evaluation systems to measure the impact of public policies and make the necessary adjustments.
- **Strengthening capacities:**Invest in the training of municipal officials so that they can develop the necessary skills to implement quality management models.
- **Citizen participation:**Promote the active participation of citizens in decision-making processes and in the evaluation of public services.

That is to say, The study highlights the importance of designing and implementing quality management models that are appropriate to the realities of small local governments and that promote citizen participation. By doing so, you can contribute to improving the quality of public services, increasing citizen confidence and strengthening the emotional stability of municipal workers. Such research has important implications for employers, workers and, ultimately, for society in general. The mimes that present the following implications for the Institutions:

- **Financial Wellness Programs:**Companies should consider implementing financial education programs to help their employees improve their financial management and reduce money-related stress.
- **Healthy work environment:**Promoting a healthy and balanced work environment, which allows employees to balance their work and personal lives, can help reduce stress and improve performance.
- **Work flexibility:**Offering flexible work options can help employees better manage their financial and personal responsibilities.
- **Economic development:**A financially healthy population contributes to economic growth and social development.

With respect to learning about accountability in budget management, in a municipality Barba-Martín et al. (2020) propose a formative evaluation model that combines self-assessment, co-assessment and hetero-assessment. They argue that this model can help students bridge the gap between theory and practice. Together, these two authors offer a comprehensive view of assessment and its role in learning. Their research suggests that evaluation can be a powerful tool to promote deep learning, but that it must be implemented in a careful and thoughtful manner that can be applied in municipal management.

In comparison with the results, the research of Lazos and Olivé (2016) proposes a knowledge society

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model for Mexico that is based on these principles. This model can help Mexico take advantage of the opportunities of the knowledge society and overcome the challenges it poses.

The studies cited in administrator, administrator et al., (2023) show that management by results, organizational learning and the knowledge society are interrelated concepts. Knowledge is essential for results-based management, and organizational learning is necessary so that organizations can adapt to the changes of the knowledge society.

Organizations that want to be successful in the knowledge society must focus on: Develop a culture of learning, Be inclusive and respectful of diversity: Organizations must be aware of cultural diversity and promote the participation of all citizens. By following these recommendations, organizations can improve their ability to achieve their objectives and contribute to the development of the knowledge society.

V. Conclusion

The implementation of concerted strategic planning at the local level, together with the promotion of learning and accountability in budget management, represents a unique opportunity to improve the quality of life of local communities. By combining these elements, a more transparent, efficient and oriented public management model can be built to the needs of citizens.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

All coauthors have contributed to this article.

Financing of the research: With own resources.

Declaration of interests: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest that could have influenced the results obtained or the interpretations proposed.

Declaration of informed consent

The study was conducted in accordance with the Code of ethics and good publishing practices.

Usability

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